

The Impact of Organizational Agility Dimensions on Employees' Job Satisfaction in Private Universities in Lebanon

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Abstract:- Nothing has ever been more constant than change. In our day and age, change is more of a way of life than a passing fad. This study focuses on examining the impact of four dimensions of organizational agility on employees' job satisfaction. Responsiveness, competency, flexibility, and quickness are these four dimensions. on this basis, theoretical and practical researches were conducted. A questionnaire was distributed via Internet among employees that are working in Lebanese private universities. The survey embraced questions measuring each dimension of organizational agility as well as employees' satisfaction towards their jobs. This study data was collected from random employees working in private universities in Lebanon. Organizational agility dimensions, employees' job satisfaction and the relation between them was measured depending on the overall collected responses; which was 459. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics with the help of SPSS statistics software. As a result, for the data analysis findings, it has been determined organizational agility as a whole and each of its dimensions, responsiveness, competency, flexibility, and quickness, separately have a significant and positive influence on employees' job satisfaction.

Keywords:- *Organizational Agility, Responsiveness, Competency, Flexibility, Quickness, Employee Job Satisfaction.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Global economies and societies have altered dramatically in the previous decade at every level. Following the massive technological breakthroughs and inventions that we see on a daily basis, we are seeing daily signs of substantial shifts in how everything functions around us. Globalization and digitalization have facilitated this transition. Since the end of 2019, the world has been combating the unique Coronavirus "COVID-19" pandemic. Huge and extraordinary changes in the way businesses work have occurred since then. This pandemic has caused enormous economies to go online while global measures for preventing individual interaction have been put in place all around the world.

In a similar line, it is expected that the techniques and styles that have been utilized in organizations since the beginning would be changed as a result of these enormous changes and alterations. Organizations must adapt to changes in their environment in order to continue operating successfully and efficiently. The value of the agility construct became apparent, yet most firms have been ignoring it for years. Organizational agility is described as an organization's capacity to quickly and effectively adapt to changes in its environment and turn those changes into future possibilities (Belasco, 1990; Goldman et al., 1995; Sharifi & Zhang, 1999; Worley et al., 2014; Rademakers et al., 2019).

To be able to adopt new strategies and plans that match with the continuously and fast changing demands and desires of consumers, firms must maintain high levels of job satisfaction among their employees in order for them to understand and adapt to the changes (Azkia & Tavakoli, 2006). Most firms place an emphasis on employee performance while ignoring their contentment and work satisfaction. Employee job satisfaction is commonly defined as the pleasurable and favorable feelings that occur in an employee as a result of positive assessments. Job satisfaction is regarded as a critical construct to examine and comprehend, both conceptually and empirically, because it is linked to numerous variables that influence the overall performance and efficiency of companies.

There have been very few studies that investigate the relationship between organizational agility and employee job satisfaction. This gap gave rise to the significance of this study, which will conduct research to analyze the relationship between the two concepts. Maintaining high levels of job satisfaction for employees is intimately tied to attaining the organization's goals and objectives in today's ever-changing world. As a result, firms must now investigate the relationship and influence of embracing organizational agility on employee job satisfaction in order to comprehend them and develop the appropriate strategies and action plans to grow and prosper.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Organizational Agility

Organizations are confronting greater changes every day as a result of globalization, which has made change an everlasting fact in human existence. According to Lawler and Worley (2006), globalization has increased the level of competitiveness among industries by opening up new global markets and dealing with global consumers. As a result, incorporating agile techniques is regarded as a requirement in order to compete and survive in the market (Sharifi & Zhang, 1999). Most prior studies and researches agreed on the general definition of agility as: the ability to respond to change in a timely manner.

Traditional normal organizations are known for their slow responsiveness to change and rigidity, owing to their use of the flow-down hierarchy technique in operations and decision-making (Aghina et al., 2017). However, according to Sharifi & Zhang (2001), an organization's ability to feel, comprehend, and effectively adapt to current and anticipated market changes is required to continue its growth and success. As a result of this need, the idea of organizational agility was defined as a dynamic capability that allows an organization to incorporate, grow, and reconfigure internal and external capabilities in order to deal with quick and continual changes (Teece et al., 1997). In this study, OA is expressed as “the ability of an organization to competitively survive by adapting efficiently to unexpected environmental changes and proactively reacting to potential market opportunities”.

➤ Conceptual Frameworks of Organizational Agility

Six primary conceptual frameworks were chosen for this study and will be briefly explained in chronological order in order to understand the evolution of the field of organizational agility.

According to Belasco (1990), the four main elements that build up his conceptual framework are: the preparation process of the organization's management for switching from old to new strategic ways, the process of ensuring the sufficient resources for new positioning, the process creating numerical expectations in order to build a vision, and the process of managing the change at the level of organization and individual.

Goldman, Nagel, and Preiss (1995) conceptual framework also includes four main constructs with detailed sub-elements: the ability to enrich the customers' purchase experience, the process of cooperating with competitors for optimum advantage, the process of creating flexible organizational structure, and the process of leveraging the influence of people and information.

In 1999, Sharifi and Zhang introduced a significant contribution to the research of organizational agility. They classified changes into five fields: market changes, competition changes, customer requirements changes, technology changes, and social factors changes. Then they have classified the effect of the changes on three main domains: on present and ongoing activities and plans, on market share and market position, and

on organization's future plans and strategies. Four dimensions for organizational agility were introduced: responsiveness, competency, flexibility, and quickness; they are the main variables used in this study to measure the organizational agility.

Meredith and Francis (2000) framework focused on the following agile constructs: strategies, processes, linkages, and people building up the Agile Wheel Reference Model that helps organizations to identify their level or agility, what they have and what they need. Perceiving, strategizing, testing and implementing are the main four constructs of Worley et al. (2014) conceptual framework.

The last framework examined in this study was Holbeche (2015), depending on previous studies the framework embraced the focus on the following elements: Strategies, operations, people practices and linkages.

➤ Organizational Agility Dimensions

In this study, Sharifi and Zhang's (1999) categorization of dimensions is embraced. They are classified into four dimensions:

Responsiveness: the organization's capacity to consistently respond to internal and external changes, including opportunities and challenges, in a timely manner in order to sustain a persistent competitive edge (Kritchanchai et al., 1999; Shaw et al., 2003; Raschke, 2007).

Competency: It is the broad range of skills that contribute to an organization's performance, profitability, and efficiency in attaining its objectives and goals.

Flexibility: It is an organization's capacity to use the same skills to produce a variety of goods and achieve a set of objectives despite challenges (Bendoly & Jacobs, 2004).

Quickness: The ability of a company to accomplish tasks and procedures in the least amount of time possible.

B. Job Satisfaction

As a dependent and independent variable, job satisfaction has been one of the most fundamental concepts investigated in social sciences studies, particularly in organizational behavior and organizational psychology. Despite millions of studies on job satisfaction management conducted over hundreds of years, it continues to play an important part in the learning process of contemporary management. In this study, relying on previous studies, job satisfaction is defined as “the sum of pleasurable and favorable feelings arising from a positive appraisal for diverse employment aspects of a person's job experience”.

The most common dimensions for job satisfaction were discussed by Weiss et al. (1967), who classified them into three main categories: intrinsic satisfaction: this scenario is achieved through internal characteristics in employees such as willing to embrace responsibility, desire to succeed, gratitude, and etc... Extrinsic satisfaction: this situation is achieved through external variables affecting employees such as workplace conditions, salaries and compensations, administration or

supervision, and etc... General satisfaction: this scenario is achieved by satisfying both the internal and extrinsic aspects. To separate itself from its competition, a company must focus not just on increased profit and market share, but also on successfully and effectively managing its internal dynamics. Employees are the most essential resource for internal dynamics in this context (İnan, 2020).

➤ *Job Satisfaction Theories*

Job satisfaction theories have been suggested in order to define the internal and external elements that may impact employees' behavior, as well as the explanations and motivational factor that encourage job satisfaction.

1. *Scope theories:*

The theories that emphasize the role of the intentions behind an employee's particular action toward a certain situation are known as scope or content theories (Öztürk, 2020). Maslow (1943) asserted that an individual can only be energized by meeting his wants, and that his actions are affected until he meets a certain need. He identified five sorts of wants, each of which cannot be met unless the one before it is fulfilled: Physiological needs, safety needs, belongingness and love needs (social needs), esteem needs, and self-actualization needs.

Frederick Herzberg, a behavioral scientist, proposed the Two-Factor Theory, which asserts that job satisfaction and job dissatisfaction are caused by specific work elements. He divided them into two categories: Hygiene and Motivational aspects (Herzberg et al., 1959; Herzberg, 2003). Working circumstances, salary and pay, financial rewards, work policies, supervisory leadership style, inter-colleague relationships, and job security are examples of hygiene factors. Their presence does not necessarily result in job satisfaction, but their absence result in job dissatisfaction. Recognitions, achievements, success, responsibilities, and advancements are examples of motivational factors that are directly tied to the work itself and their existence results in greater job performance.

The psychologist David McClelland (1988) job satisfaction theory classified the basic needs of an individual into three main types: need for achievement, need for power and need for relationship. He believes that each employee has the three types of needs, but that depending on his or her mentality and culture, each employee is more inspired to one of them.

2. *Process theories*

The acts, interactions, and conditions that drive an individual's activities are explained by process theories (Zengin, 2020). Vroom (1964) has classified three main factors that influence motivation: expectations, instrumentality, and valency; if one or more of these three factors is absent, the individual may lack his motivation.

Porter and Lawler (1961) imply that all people are rational and that they are influenced by both internal and external stimuli. Furthermore, because each person has his or her unique desires and goals, individuals tend to choose different behaviors based on their intended outcomes.

Locke and Latham's theory of job satisfaction (1990) is made up of five main elements: clarity, challenge, commitment, feed-back, and task complexity. They believe that if companies focus on these components while defining goals, their employees will be more engaged in their work and hence content with their jobs.

➤ *Factors Affecting Job Satisfaction*

Organizations must first recognize the factors that influence job satisfaction in order to comprehend and apply it. If this were not the case, it would be difficult to achieve the desired level of performance from employees. When researching the aspects that influence employee job satisfaction, individual or personal traits must be taken into account first. As a result of their distinct personalities, past experiences, and skills, each individual has their own unique perceptions and expectations from their jobs. Age, gender, marital situation, educational level, and personality are all basic elements that influence an individual's experience (İnan, 2020). Organizational factors, in addition to individual factors, have an equal and possibly greater impact on employee job satisfaction levels. Most prior research agreed that organizational elements include all aspects relating to employment structure, salary and compensation, promotions and advancements, job safety and working environment, and finally organizational culture and interpersonal interactions.

III. METHODOLOGY

This research followed a quantitative approach, including survey research techniques. The potential population chosen for this study are all the employees working in private universities in Lebanon. In order to collect the needed data from the sample, a simple random method was used. In this study, a sample of 459 respondents have been acquired from employees working in private universities in Lebanon. Since this research is conducted based on quantitative methods, the collection of primary data was done by a survey tool using a questionnaire based on a 5 Likert-type scale.

The four dimensions of the organizational agility (Responsiveness OAR, Competency OAC, Flexibility OAF, and Quickness OAQ) are measured with a 16-item measuring tool (4 items for each dimension); and employees job satisfaction is measured with a 20-item. Regarding the demographic factors, frequency tables were created. Regarding the scales' items, descriptive statistics and analysis were conducted through: Validity test, Factor analysis, KMO and Bartlett's test, Reliability analysis, Correlation analysis, and Linear Regression analysis.

➤ *Conceptual Framework*

The following is the conceptual framework model connecting between the variables of this study:

Fig 1 Conceptual Framework

IV. FINDINGS

➤ *Descriptive statistics*

Table 1 represents the descriptive characteristics of the four dimensions of organizational agility and of the dependent variable, Job Satisfaction, in terms of Mean and Standard deviation.

Table 1 Descriptive Characteristics of Variables

Variable	N	Mean	St. Deviation
Responsiveness	459	3.7516	.78650
Competency	459	3.7059	.74788
Flexibility	459	3.5735	.80063
Quickness	459	3.4346	.87110
Job Satisfaction	459	3.2501	.58792
Valid N (listwise)	459		

➤ *Reliability findings*

A test to determine Cronbach alpha coefficient was undertaken in order to measure the reliability statistics for the Data of this study. Cronbach's alpha coefficient represents how closely a group of items are related as a whole; in other terms, it represents the internal consistency of the data items as a whole. Table 2 shows the Cronbach's alpha values for the variables of this study.

Table 2 Reliability Analysis

Number of Items	Variable	Cronbach's Alpha
4	Responsiveness	.878
4	Competency	.776
4	Flexibility	.850
4	Quickness	.890
20	Job Satisfaction	.939

➤ *Correlation Analysis*

Table 3 presents the correlation between the variables of the study. If the significance value is positive, it is assumed that there is a positive link between variables. Also, if the

significance input is higher than 0.8, the variables are considered to be substantially correlated.

Table 3 Correlation Analysis

	OAR	OAC	OAF	OAQ	JS
OAR	1				
OAC	.690*	1			
OAF	.757*	.728**	1		
OAQ	.757*	.714**	.809*	1	
JS	.837*	.814**	.880*	.852**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

➤ *Regression Analysis (separately)*

Table 4 represents the regression analysis findings for the four dimensions of the independent variable separately.

Table 4 Models' summary (separately)

Variable Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.837 ^a	.701	.700	.32205
2	.814 ^b	.663	.662	.34175
3	.880 ^c	.774	.774	.27957
4	.852 ^d	.726	.725	.30810

a. Predictors: (Constant), Responsiveness
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Competency
 c. Predictors: (Constant), Flexibility
 d. Predictors: (Constant), Quickness

Model 1 represents Organizational Agility Responsiveness as the predictor of job satisfaction. Findings show that responsiveness has a positive relationship to job satisfaction ($\beta = .626$; $p < 0.001$). R square value of this model is 0.837, which means that the model explains 83.7% of the variance in job satisfaction. Values from ANOVA test ($F = 1069.369$; $p < 0.001$) also support the statistical significance of the explained variance.

Model 2 represents Organizational Agility Competency as the predictor of job satisfaction. Findings show that Competency has a positive relationship to job satisfaction ($\beta = .640$; $p < 0.001$). R square value of this model is 0.663, which means that the model explains 66.3% of the variance in job satisfaction. Values from ANOVA test ($F = 898.425$; $p < 0.001$) also support the statistical significance of the explained variance.

Model 3 represents Organizational Agility Flexibility as the predictor of job satisfaction. Findings show that Flexibility has a positive relationship to job satisfaction ($\beta = .646$; $p < 0.001$). R square value of this model is 0.774, which means that

the model explains 77.4% of the variance in job satisfaction. Values from ANOVA test ($F= 1568.397$; $p < 0.001$) also support the statistical significance of the explained variance.

Model 4 represents Organizational Agility Quickness as the predictor of job satisfaction. Findings show that Quickness has a positive relationship to job satisfaction ($\beta = .575$; $p < 0.001$). R square value of this model is 0.726, which means that the model explains 72.6% of the variance in job satisfaction. Values from ANOVA test ($F= 1210.686$; $p < 0.001$) also support the statistical significance of the explained variance.

➤ *Regression Analysis (combined)*

Table 5 presents the findings of the regression analysis conducted to all the dimensions combined together

Table 5 Model’s Summary (combined)

Variable Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
5	.943 ^a	.888	.887	.19726
a.Predictors: (Constant), OAQ, OAC, OAR, OAF				

Model 5 represents Organizational Agility, as a whole (dimensions are combined), as the predictor of job satisfaction. Findings show that organizational agility has a positive relationship to job satisfaction ($p < 0.001$). R square value of this model is 0.888, which means that the model explains 88.8% of the variance in job satisfaction. Values from ANOVA test ($F = 903.611$; $p < 0.001$) also support the statistical significance of the explained variance.

➤ *Hypotheses testing*

Table 6 represents the findings of examining the hypotheses:

Table 6 Hypotheses Testing

Hypotheses	Statement	Result
H1	There is a significant positive relationship between responsiveness and employees’ job satisfaction	Supported
H2	There is a significant positive relationship between competency and employees’ job satisfaction	Supported
H3	There is a significant positive relationship between flexibility and employees’ job satisfaction	Supported
H4	There is a significant positive relationship between quickness and employees’ job satisfaction	Supported
H5	There is a significant positive relationship between organizational agility and employees’ job satisfaction	Supported

V. CONCLUSION

The purpose of this study is to analyze the influence of organizational agility dimensions on employee job satisfaction at private universities in Lebanon. Organizational agility responsiveness, organizational agility competency, organizational agility flexibility, and organizational agility quickness were all tested. A survey was undertaken, and questionnaires were provided to a sample of employees, in order to examine their impact on employee job satisfaction. The information gathered from their responses was scrutinized and analyzed. The analytical results are examined in order to evaluate the study’s research questions and hypotheses.

➤ *Hypothesis (H1):*

According to the results of the regression analysis, the organizational agility responsiveness (OAR) variable has a substantial impact on job satisfaction of employees working at private universities in Lebanon. This discovery is congruent with the findings of Nikpour and Salajegheh’s investigation (2010). They believe that organizations that can detect changes and challenges efficiently and respond to them reactively and proactively will be able to endure and persist in the market for longer periods of time, which will affect the stability and job satisfaction levels of the employees who work in these organizations. We can conclude that firms that can anticipate changes and plan their operations appropriately provide their employees with the proper working circumstances by attempting to reduce or eliminate possible risk and obstacles. As a result, employees are more relaxed, motivated in their jobs, and happy.

➤ *Hypothesis (H2):*

According to the findings of the regression study, organizational agility competency (OAC) has a substantial impact on job satisfaction of employees working at private universities in Lebanon. This discovery backs with prior study by Yusuf et al (1999). They feel that organizations with high levels of competency have an impact on job satisfaction. We can conclude that employee job satisfaction is increased when they work in firms that embrace diverse qualities in order to accomplish goals and vision. The technological facilities required, operational effectiveness, change management initiatives, and other capacities that enable achievement of goals and objectives are examples of capabilities that make employees’ jobs more pleasant and rewarding.

➤ *Hypothesis (H3):*

According to the findings of the regression analysis, the organizational agility flexibility (OAF) variable has a substantial impact on job satisfaction of employees working at private universities in Lebanon. This notion backs with prior studies by Gunasekaran and Yusuf (2002). They believe that building, company procedures, and tactics that are flexible improve job satisfaction. Employees in firms that accept flexibility in their everyday procedures and activities, as well as strategic plans, have better levels of job satisfaction. Such firms provide a flexible workplace by taking into account all of their surrounds and changing their plans accordingly, as well as efficiently utilizing their resources to produce original and innovative products. Being a part of such an organization

boosts creativity and opens up prospects for future promotion, leading in increased job satisfaction.

➤ *Hypothesis (H4):*

According to the regression study, the organizational agility quickness (OAQ) variable has a substantial impact on job satisfaction of employees working at private colleges in Lebanon. Zargar's (2001) research backs up this idea, claiming that speed in delivering products/services, as well as speed in procedures and activities, leads to increased job satisfaction. We might conclude that people who work in firms that value speed in their activities and procedures have greater levels of job satisfaction. Organizations that are characterized quick or fast are those that adapt to changes in the quickest amount of time possible. Employees are consequently more motivated to continue up with the organization's pace and work harder, resulting in improved job performance and higher job satisfaction.

➤ *Hypothesis (H5):*

According to the results of the regression study, the independent variable, organizational agility (OA), has a substantial impact on the dependent variable, job satisfaction of employees working at private universities in Lebanon. Nabatchian et al. (2014) found similar results when analyzing the association between organizational agility and job satisfaction. Their sample consisted of personnel from Iran's Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports. Despite the fact that the two studies target distinct groups, they both confirm the link between organizational agility and employee job satisfaction.

To evaluate the association between the two variables, the predictors in the organizational agility regression analysis were the four dimensions: responsiveness, competency, flexibility, and quickness. Overall, businesses are deemed agile if they adopt efficient response to external changes, acquire and grow the necessary competencies, incorporate flexibility in operations and processes, and prioritize job completion speed. Such firms provide a comfortable and pleasant working environment for their employees, which improves their skills and talents and hence increases their job satisfaction.

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